

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE REFORM OF 1918 AND ITS IMPACT ON POLITICAL SCIENCES: LATIN AMERICAN IDENTITY, HIGHER EDUCATION AND THE FIGHT FOR SOCIAL JUSTICE

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Abstract

The objective of this research work is to analyze the University Reform of 1918 from the perspective of political sciences. It seeks to understand the fundamental role that the university played in the construction of Latin American identity and in the fight for more just societies. The ideas of José Vasconcelos and Víctor Raúl Haya de la Torre, two key figures of the reformist movement, will be analyzed and their validity in the current context will be evaluated. This study is framed in the analysis of the relationships between higher education, politics and society in Latin America. Concepts such as university autonomy, co-government, academic freedom, university extension, Latin American identity, social justice, among others, will be addressed. A qualitative methodology will be used, based on bibliographic analysis of primary and secondary sources. Documents from the time, texts by the aforementioned authors, and academic studies on the Reform of 1918 will be analyzed. The results of the study will allow us to understand the impact of the Reform on political science, on the construction of Latin American identity and on the fight for social justice. Conclusions The University Reform of 1918 constituted a fundamental milestone in the history of Latin America. Its impact on political sciences has been significant, contributing to the construction of a more democratic, critical and socially committed university. The ideas of José Vasconcelos and Víctor Raúl Haya de la Torre continue to be relevant to think about the role of higher education in the 21st century, in a context of great challenges for the region.

Keywords: University Reform of 1918, political science, Latin American identity, higher education.

Introduction

In this work we address The University Reform of 1918 and Latin American thought to do so by engaging in a dialogue with the authors José Vasconcelos and Víctor Raúl Haya de la Torre, taking into account the context we intend to analyze and describe the point of view that these authors assumed regarding this historical fact. (or historical process). The study of the University Reform is relevant because it is a current of Latin American projection that generates libertarian, critical knowledge with a continental dimension. The student movement became a leading actor of its time, forming groups and federations to fight for education.

Investigation

The University Reform was a heterogeneous movement that manifested itself differently in each university. In the UBA, the reformist movement was characterized by its opposition to positivism, while, in Córdoba, anticlericalism was an important factor. Overall, the Reformation was driven by a broad spectrum of political and social positions that rejected the traditional order¹. The reform questioned the elitism and exclusion present in the universities of the time, advocating the

active participation of students in university government and the opening of classrooms to traditionally marginalized sectors. This democratization laid the foundations for greater citizen participation and the construction of more just and inclusive societies. Pérez Gamón Carolina (2023) when we talk about citizenship we can mention "...*Thomas Marshall reflecting on the How citizenship status was established in relationship with the institutions of capitalism. Concerned about the problem of inequality, he postulates the concept of social inequality. citizenship to account for the social foundations that must be built to guarantee democracy. Thus, we observe a sequence of changes that oscillate between two poles: on the one hand, an interruption in the process of building society citizenship that particularly affects excluded sectors the system or close to its collapse, and on the other, an expansion in the field of social rights for those sectors included, that is, those who managed to join the new social welfare scenario - generated by the market- benefiting from the new rules of the game I will suggest that in our current society it is assumed that both remain compatible, to the point that, in a way, Citizens themselves have become the architects of legitimate social society inequality...*"².

¹ Recalde A. (2018) "La Universidad y la integración sudamericana", en El legado reformista en las nuevas universidades del conurbano, EDUNPAZ, Buenos Aires.p.170

² Pérez Gamón, C. M. (2023). Evolution of the Notion of Citizenship in Latin America and Effect in Argentina. International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research and Studies, 3(4), p.799. Retrieved from www.multiresearchjournal

*José Vasconcelos*³⁴

“Córdoba is one of the main centers of that famous university student movement that has spread throughout South America and now reaches Cuba.”

We present a brief biography of José Vasconcelos, which can be expanded by consulting Aritz Recalde “Life and Work of Vasconcelos”, he was a prominent Mexican intellectual, writer and politician born in Oaxaca (1881-1959) Mexico. His life and work have great relevance in the history of Mexico and, by extension, in Latin America. Highlighted below are some key aspects of his life and his importance in the region: He studied philosophy at the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM) and then at the Sorbonne University in Paris. Upon his return to Mexico, he assumed important academic positions at UNAM, including rector; he was a defender of education and culture. His exile took him to Havana, Cuba after the coup d'état of 1913 and the death of Madero. He also took refuge in Argentina and received an invitation from the National University of La Plata and Alfredo Palacios. He was also hired by Natalio Botana's newspaper *Crítica*⁵.

He assumes the task of the educational renewal of his country and the region as well as interpreting popular aspirations along with political commitment. He was rector of the National Autonomous University of Mexico between June 1920 and October 1921. This can be seen in his speech “...*I am in these moments, more than a new rector who succeeds the previous ones, a delegate of the Revolution who does not come to seek refuge to meditate in the quiet atmosphere of the classrooms, but to invite you to go out with him, to the fight, to you sharing the responsibilities and efforts with us. At this time I do not come to work for the University, but to ask the University to work for the people. The people have been supporting the University and now they need it, and through me they come to ask advice...*” (Recalde Aritz 2021. p. 207)

At UNAM, Vasconcelos returned to the ideas developed at the Youth Ateneo (such as the public communication of knowledge) founded together with Antonio Caso, Alfonso Reyes and Pedro Henríquez Ureña, among others who created the Popular University in 1912. For him the University was the one who organized, coordinated the teaching. His actions as rector were concrete and effective by creating soup kitchens, he was ensuring that students with few resources could have access to food, essential for their physical and

mental development. By freeing them from paying college fees, he was removing a major barrier to higher education. And by allowing wealthy students to pay high fees to cover the expenses of those with few financial resources, he was creating a system of solidarity that benefited everyone.

Within the framework of the university reform of 1918, he promoted the exchange departments, the Summer School for foreigners and the University Extension Department. She considered that the implementation of these measures would contribute to the solution of social problems” ...*The problems come to her not only to be investigated, but also to be resolved...*” (...) “...*The Hispanic American university student cannot exempt himself from contact human, even occasional, through technical advice, conference, speech and book...*”⁶.

Furthermore, the author adds, The Shield of the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM) will consist of a map of Latin America, a symbol of identity and pride for Mexicans. It was created in 1921 by Vasconcelos, who expressed in it his Spanish-American ideology. from Mexico to the southern part of the Argentine Republic” ...With the legend “For my race the spirit will speak.” This motto means the conviction that our race will develop a culture of new trends, with a spiritual and very free essence. An eagle and a condor will hold the shield, all supported by an allegory of the cactus and the Aztec cactus...”⁷.

Influence of the preaching of Vasconcelos and the Ateneo de la Juventud on the events of 1918 in Argentina and Mexico-

Advancing through Aritz Recalde's text we were able to observe that the preaching of José Vasconcelos and the men of the Ateneo de la Juventud had a significant influence on the events of 1918 in Argentina and Mexico. In both countries, university students were inspired by Vasconcelos's thinking to demand educational and political reforms.

In Argentina, the university reform of 1918 aimed to modernize the university and make it more democratic. The reformist students, known as the “young people of 1918”, opposed the elitism and authoritarianism of the traditional university. They sought a more

³ LA PRENSA 04-02-2020, disponible <https://www.laprensa.com.ar/485409-Jose-Vasconcelos-el-maestro-mexicano-de-la-juventud-de-America.note.aspx>

⁴ Vasconcelos José y la Universidad capítulo VIII. p.214

⁵ Vasconcelos José y la Universidad capítulo VIII. pp. 205-206

⁶ Ibid., Capítulo VIII p.209

⁷ Se puede ver en detalle las partes del Escudo UNAM y su significado en el Capítulo VIII pp.209-210

accessible education for all social sectors, as well as greater student participation in university life.

In Mexico, he was one of the main promoters of the educational reform of 1921. This reform sought to create a more secular and nationalist education.

Vasconcelos also had a personal relationship with several of the protagonists of the events of 1918 in Argentina. Among them were Alfredo Palacios, an Argentine lawyer and politician who was one of the leaders of university reform, and Manuel Ugarte, an Argentine writer and journalist who was an advocate of Latin American unity.

Vasconcelos' preaching was a source of inspiration for Argentine reformist students since he defended education as a universal right and as an instrument of social transformation. In his work *The Cosmic Race*, he praised the universality of the doctrine of the University of Buenos Aires, as well as its renewal of methods and its constant importation of foreign notables. In *The Cosmic Race* he considered that "the greatest contemporary focus of Latin American culture is found in Buenos Aires." "The Argentine University surpasses the others in America not only because of the luxury of its material construction or because of the salaries it pays to its professors and the freedom it allows them in teaching; also for the universality of its doctrine and the renewal of methods and the constant importation of foreign notables. "There is almost no illustrious professor from a Spanish university who has not given courses in Argentina."⁸

Vasconcelos expressed his admiration for the Reform, but also noted some differences with his own vision of the university.

Firstly, he did not agree with student participation in university co-government, arguing that this could distract students from their main objective, which is academic training. In his book *From Robinson to Odysseus*, he stated "there is nothing that relaxes both school discipline and student intervention in the administrative functions of the university."⁹ Instead, he proposed that students have a voice in university councils, but without vote.

Secondly, it considers that the University Reform is a movement that has a deeper meaning than a mere reform of university management and highlights the role of the Reform in promoting the values of continental unity, anti-imperialist consciousness and commitment with workers' struggles.

Advancing the reading of Aritz Recalde, the International Student Meeting of 1921, organized by José Vasconcelos, was a significant event in the history of

Latin America. The Congress, which included the participation of students from across the region, reaffirmed the students' commitment to university reform and the fight for social justice. It also contributed to the spread of socialist and anti-imperialist ideas in the region.

The largest groups were those from Argentina, Mexico and Peru. The Argentine delegation was chaired by Héctor Ripa Alberdi, who was accompanied by Arnaldo Orfila Reynal, Enrique Dreysin and Pablo Vrillaud.

The Congress approved 7 resolutions, of which 6 reflected the model of socialist ideas that the meeting acquired, while the last resolution founded the International Federation of Students and included issues of its organization. In addition, the II International Student Congress was convened to be held in Buenos Aires. in the year 1922. The Federation of Latin American Intellectuals, founded in 1921 by José Vasconcelos, aimed to promote the cultural and political unity of the region. However, its objectives were not fully achieved due to a number of factors, including youth interns, political instability on the continent, and lack of support from governments. Despite this, the Federation left an important legacy to the extent that it forged links between thinkers and institutions that continued to work for the unity of the region. José Vasconcelos' university project was a radical proposal for his time. He moved away from the traditional university model, which focused on the training of intellectual elites, to propose a university linked to the social reality of the country and committed to social change.

From what the author has stated we can infer that the fundamental principles of the Vasconcelos project can be summarized in the following points:

Link with social reality: The university had to address the specific problems faced by the Mexican people.

Comprehensive training: The university had to train integral citizens, capable of thinking critically, acting ethically and contributing to the development of society.

Leadership for social change: The university had to train a new generation of leaders capable of promoting reforms that would improve the lives of Mexicans" ...The University and intellectuals had to contribute to the political and cultural unity of Latin America and the emergence of "cosmic race." Consistent with this ideology, he promoted meetings and congresses of youth and intellectuals and accompanied leaders like Haya de la Torre, who made the cause of South American unity a central pillar of their program..."¹⁰.

⁸ Ibid., p.214

⁹Ibid., p.214

¹⁰ Ibid., p.221

*Victor Raúl Haya de la Torre*¹¹

Raúl Haya de La Torre was a Peruvian intellectual and politician, founder of the Peruvian Aprista Party (PAP). He was born in Trujillo, Peru, in 1895, and died in Lima in 1979. In his youth, Haya de la Torre stood out as a student leader. He was president of the University Federation of Trujillo and founder of the González Prada Popular Universities. These universities, created in 1921, aimed to educate the Peruvian popular sectors, especially workers, peasants and indigenous people¹². Words from Haya de la Torre made student speeches about the Reform "...The University Reform which in essence was the first cry for emancipation of our "mental colony"—herald of a new consciousness in Indo-America—expressively described the old universities and their watertight pedagogical methods as "the viceroalties of the spirit..."¹³.

In 1924, Haya de la Torre founded the PAP in Mexico, with the support of the Mexican philosopher and politician José Vasconcelos. APRA is a left-wing political party that defends the rights of workers, peasants and indigenous people. He was a charismatic and controversial leader. Its ideology, known as aprismo, was influenced by socialism, indigenism and Americanism. Aprismo had a great impact on Peruvian and Latin American politics.

Contribution to the APRA foundation

The founding of APRA was a milestone in Peruvian political history. APRA is one of the most important political parties in Peruvian history and has had a great impact on the country's political life. Haya de la Torre's contribution to the founding of APRA was fundamental "...The founding programmatic bases of APRA have aspects of the reformist ideology, to which are also added slogans of nationalism that would later be raised by other political forces: fight against Imperialism, for the political unity of Latin America, for the Nationalization of lands and industries, for the Internationalization of the Panama Canal, for solidarity with all the oppressed peoples and classes of the world..."¹⁴.

Haya de la Torre was a promoter of popular education and social justice. His contributions to popular

education were the following: He promoted the creation of the González Prada Popular Universities, which aimed to educate the popular sectors. These universities were an innovative model that allowed people with limited resources to access higher education.

For de la Torre, the Reform was the "...most transcendent movement of intellectual renewal that occurred in Indian America since Independence. A gallant and intrepid generation of twenty-somethings spoke to the Indian-American students and workers in an unusual language but one that they all understood. And he proclaimed the "sacred right to insurrection..."¹⁵.

While in Mexico, he laid the foundations of the APRA continental organization according to the same guidelines as the popular universities. On May 7, 1924, before traveling to Europe, he made known to the young people and submitted to consensus the motto "joint action of the Indo-American peoples." *for the political and economic union of our twenty-one states* ... "We not only want our united America but also our fair America... That flag that I give you, comrades Mexican students... you have here; The red will say of the palpating aspirations for justice that in this admirable hour of the world inflames the conscience of the people and that our generation proclaims with the new humanity... On the wide red field the figure in gold of the Indo-American nation, points out the vast lands, that united and strong, will provide a home without inequalities to all the children of the human race. Accept it because it is ours. It will flame first over the dreaming crowds of youth that are opening the way, and later it will be the people... who shake it in the trembling tumult of their struggles. I give it to you, fellow students of Mexico, because it is you... who have the right to wear it. Because you are children of the people who most gallantly defended the freedom of the race; because from your own blood emerged the example of a new egalitarian and advancing society. Forget who gave it to you, but always remember that it is a symbol of youth, justice and unity..."¹⁶.

¹¹ Ideele Revista N°277, disponible: <https://revistaideele.com/ideele/content/123-a%C3%B1os-del-natalicio-de-haya-de-la-torre>

¹² Haya de La Torre Raúl y la universidad reformista (Apunte de clase 2 de la EPNyL, Aritz Recalde).

¹³ Haya de la Torre Raúl 2010 Treinta Años del Aprismo. Fondo Editorial del Congreso Lima -Perú, p.114

¹⁴ Haya de La Torre Raúl y la universidad reformista (Apunte de clase 2 de la EPNyL, Aritz Recalde)

¹⁵ Ibid., p.3

¹⁶ Haya de la Torre Raúl 2010 Treinta Años del Aprismo. Fondo Editorial del Congreso Lima -Perú.

Conclusion.

The preaching of Vasconcelos and the Ateneo de la Juventud had a significant influence on the events of 1918 in Argentina and Mexico. Reformist students in both countries were inspired by Vasconcelos's thinking to demand educational and political reforms, and Vasconcelos himself was one of the main promoters of the 1921 educational reform in Mexico.

In the context of the time in which it was created, the UNAM shield was a symbol of hope for a better future for Latin America. Vasconcelos believed that the region could overcome its differences and build a common homeland, based on the values of culture and spirituality. It is a reminder that we share a common history and culture, and that we have the potential to build a better future for all.

Vasconcelos' university project was a radical proposal for his time. It moved away from the traditional university model, which focused on the training of intellectual elites. Instead, Vasconcelos sought to create a university that would be at the service of the Mexican people and that would contribute to the construction of a more just and egalitarian society.

The legacy of Víctor Raúl Haya de la Torre in the University Reform has transformed Latin American higher education. His ideas about university autonomy, student participation and connection with society have inspired generations of students and academics, and have contributed to universities being more democratic, inclusive and committed to social development.

Both intellectuals promoted on the continent, Pérez Gamón Carolina (2024) "...*Patriotism implies promoting the common values that share the region. This can be achieved by promoting education about history and culture, making known the thoughts and actions carried out by these men who promoted dialogue and cooperation between countries, thus giving citizens a sense of belonging...*"¹⁷.

The University Reform of 1918 marked a before and after in the history of Latin American higher education. Its ideals of democracy, autonomy, social connection and pedagogical renewal continue to be relevant in the 21st century, inspiring the universities of the region to assume a critical, proactive and committed role with the social, economic and cultural development of their communities.

Perez Gamon Carolina 2023 "...*The university world was then essentially male, while in the 21st century the growth of female enrollment increased exponentially. But there is certainly something that unites us*

with the reformist movement and that is the aspiration to build a better world, a University, with a commitment to cultural and scientific life..."¹⁸

Despite the progress made, there are still challenges ahead to consolidate reformist principles and build higher education that is more fair, equitable and relevant to the needs of the 21st century. In this sense, analysis from the perspective of political science is essential to understand the scope and limitations of the reform, as well as to identify new strategies that allow strengthening university autonomy, promoting social participation.

The results of this research transcend the mere conceptual framework and open new challenges regarding the direction of Higher Education in Latin America.

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